

**DAMAGE TO THE NERVOUS SYSTEM AND CHANGES IN THE LIVER AS A RESULT OF
POISONING BY ARSENIC ENTERING THE BODY**

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ABSTRACT

Arsenic is ranked first among toxicants posing a significant potential threat to human health based on known or suspected toxicity. This naturally occurring metalloid is a known poison, a co-carcinogen, and in lower concentrations has been shown to increase susceptibility to cognitive dysfunction. Currently, the permitted concentration of arsenic in water is 10 µg/L (10 ppb). Arsenic (As) is a common environmental contaminant widely distributed around the world. Human exposure to this metalloid comes from well water and contaminated soil, from fish and other sea organisms rich in methylated arsenic species, and from occupational exposure. Research We conducted experiments on 15 white rats weighing 140-260 g, kept in the vivarium under normal conditions at the Scientific Research Center of the Azerbaijan Medical University, and divided them into 3 groups. We determined malondialdehyde (MDA), diene conjugates (DC), which are lipid peroxidation (LPO) products, and catalase, which is an antioxidant product, in blood taken from experimental animals.

Keywords - arsenic, poisoning, nervous system, liver, treatment.

It has been reported that human arsenic exposure causes several health problems such as cancer, liver damage, dermatosis, and nervous system disturbances such as polyneuropathy, EEG abnormalities and, in extreme cases, hallucinations, disorientation and agitation [1, 2].

Arsenic intoxication can be divided into acute exposure and chronic exposure, which have different influences on the central nervous system (CNS) and the peripheral nervous system (PNS). Acute intoxication may cause conscious disturbance in the CNS and demyelinating and axon-degenerating neuropathy in the PNS. Chronic exposure may induce intellectual deterioration and neurobehavioral disorders in the CNS and axon-degenerating neuropathy in the PNS. Acute, large dose arsenic exposure may cause death, or neurological complications from which recovery is slow and incomplete. Chronic, small dose arsenic exposure may induce mild neurological changes which may be difficult to be detected in some studies. Because the longest nerve is first involved in the course of polyneuropathy and sensory involvement is more prominent in chronic arsenic neuropathy, decreased amplitude of sural sensory action potential in a nerve conduction velocity study might be the first sign of chronic arsenic PNS intoxication [3].

Arsenic causes hepatocellular disorders in many ways. Although mechanism(s) by which arsenic induces such pathological changes in the liver remains poorly understood, the common phenomenon that has emerged is the role of toxic reactive oxygen species (ROS). Chronic arsenic exposure is also associated with neurodegeneration. Peripheral neuropathy is common in persons exposed to arsenic contaminated drinking water-induced chronic toxicity [4]. Oxidative damage is also considered a likely cause of arsenic-induced brain damage because the brain is believed to be particularly vulnerable to oxidative stress due to high oxygen consumption rate and high level of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), and relatively high rate of oxygen free radical generation without commensurate levels of antioxidant defenses [5, 6]. Drug accessibility to specific target organs restricts the selection of drug permeabilities through the gastrointestinal tract and blood brain barrier. Bioavailability of drugs can be improved when they are administered intravenously upon entrapment in liposomes [7].

Arsenic and liver disorders: The liver is the major site of arsenic metabolism, showing a dose-response accumulation of this metalloid and its metabolites, possibly related with overexpression of iAs(III)-transporters, such as aquaglyceroporin-9 (AQP9) in response to iAs exposure. A main consequence of chronic

high-level arsenic exposure is NCIPH that is a result of chronic microangiopathy of portal vein branches, leading to intrahepatic portal vein occlusion. In agreement with this, populations with elevated ingest of arsenic in drinking water have a high prevalence of NCIPH in presence of skin arsenicosis [8, 9].

Studies employing isolated rat hepatocytes showed that iAs(III) promotes reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and lipid peroxidation, possibly associated with a disruption of mitochondrial membrane potential [10, 11, 12]. In a similar manner, mitochondria are the main ROS-source in rat liver cell line exposed to MMA(III); whereas in the same cellular model, DMA(III) treatment promotes ROS formation and stress in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). Animal models exposed to iAs by drinking water showed increased ROS production, malondialdehyde (MDA) accumulation, elevated protein oxidation, low levels of glutathione (GSH), and decreased glutathione peroxidase (GSH-Px), glutathione reductase (GR), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and catalase (CAT) activities in the liver compared to control animals [13, 14].

Materials and Methods

Research We conducted experiments on 15 white rats weighing 140-260 g, kept in the vivarium under normal conditions at the Scientific Research Center of the Azerbaijan Medical University, and divided them into 3 groups.

While conducting experiments, the rules of behavior with experimental animals of the European Bioethical Commission (Strasbourg 1986) and the local bioethical commission of the Azerbaijan Medical University were strictly followed. In all cases, the experiments were performed under anesthesia conditions, and at the end of the experiment, anesthesia was created by injecting 0.5 ml of calypsol solution into their abdominal cavity. The white rats selected for the experiment were divided into 3 groups with 5 heads in each.

Group 1 included intact rats.

Creation of a pathological model in rats as a result of poisoning with arsenic-contaminated water in group 2.

Changes in biochemical indicators of lipid peroxidation products in the blood of white rats in group 3 were studied 10 days after cessation of poisoning.

We determined malondialdehyde (MDA), diene conjugates (DC), which are lipid peroxidation (LPO) products, and catalase, which is an antioxidant product, in blood taken from experimental animals.

Results and Discussion

As a result of the analyses, it was determined that the concentration of MDA in the blood taken from white rats in group 1, as a result of arsenic-contaminated drinking water, varied between 1-1.5 nmol/ml, with an average quantitative indicator of 1.26 ± 0.08 nmol/ml, and the concentration of DK varied between 1.35-2.4 D232/ml, with an average quantitative indicator of 1.62 ± 0.20 D232/ml.

The concentration of MDA in the blood taken from white rats in group 2 increased by 428.6% ($p < 0.01$) compared to the intact state, ranging from a minimum of 4.9 to a maximum of 9.4 nmol/ml. From the statistical analysis of the obtained quanti-

tative indicators, it is known that the average quantitative indicator of the concentration of MDA in the blood reached 6.66 ± 0.76 nmol / ml.

In group 2, the concentration of DK increased by 25.3% ($p > 0.05$) compared to the intact state, ranging from 1.85-2.2 D232/ml, with an average quantitative indicator of 2.03 ± 0.06 D232/ml.

The concentration of MDA, a lipid peroxidation product, in the blood taken from rats in group 3 increased by 68.9% ($p > 0.05$) compared to the intact state, varying between 1.28-3.53 nmol/ml, reaching an average quantitative value of 2.13 ± 0.43 nmol/ml.

In group 3, the concentration of DK increased by 76.5% ($p < 0.01$) compared to the intact state, ranging from a minimum of 2.5 to a maximum of 3.5 D232/ml. As a result of statistical calculations, it was determined that the average quantitative indicator of DK concentration was 2.86 ± 0.17 D232/ml.

The concentration of catalase, a representative of the antioxidant defense system, in the blood taken from white rats in group 1 ranged between 2.64-2.75 mkat/l, with an average quantitative value of 2.69 ± 0.02 mkat/l.

In white rats included in group 2, the concentration of catalase in the blood taken after the poisoning model was created increased by 7.7% ($p > 0.05$) compared to the intact state, ranging from a minimum of 1.7 to a maximum of 4.6 mkat/l, with an average quantitative indicator of 2.90 ± 0.49 mkat/l.

In white rats included in group 3, the concentration of catalase in the blood taken after the creation of the model increased by 6.2% ($p > 0.05$) compared to the intact state, but in contrast to the intact state, it decreased by 1.4% ($p > 0.05$) compared to intoxication.

It was determined that the concentration of catalase in the blood of experimental animals in group 3 varied between 2.04-3.7 mkat/l. Its average quantitative indicator was 2.86 ± 0.27 mkat/l.

Conclusions:

The results of our experiments show that as a result of arsenic poisoning, lipid peroxidation products increase in blood taken from the portal vein of the liver.

Regarding the treatment of arsenic exposure, the chelation therapy has been showed to improve outcomes whether started in minutes to hours after arsenic exposure. The classic antidote against acute arsenic poisoning is BAL (British anti-Lewisite or dimercaptopropanol). However, due to the rather high toxicity of BAL, and the necessity of frequent and inconvenient intramuscular administrations, the clinical use of this drug is currently restricted to only the initial treatment for few days after acute iAs intoxications.

Nowadays, the treatment for acute intoxication uses sodium 2, 3-dimercaptopropane-1-sulfonate (DMPS) and meso-2, 3-dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA) as chelating antidotes. No treatment of proven benefit is currently available to treat chronic arsenic toxicity. Treatment options advocated are vitamin and mineral supplements and antioxidant therapy. In cases of chronic arsenic poisoning, one should consider

BAL as a chelator the signs of arsenicosis are severe or the patient is in complications.

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